

REACTIVITY OF SARS-Co-V2 COVID 19 UNDER CLIMATE CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Links may exist between the effects of climatic conditions and the epidemiological spread of the COVID 19 pandemic. The first part of the analysis consists of day-to-day monitoring of pandemic fluctuations over a period of two months in the main cluster of coronavirus in north-eastern France. The second part of the investigation is a comparative analysis for 27 European countries, of the effect of climatic conditions, temperature and humidity on the differences in the extent of the disease.

Keywords: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, Vapor, Model, humidity, Propagation

INTRODUCTION

The medical community has carried out today in the world, very numerous and important works for decades through the successive appearances of the different forms of Coronavirus. But although the latest medical studies have been widely increased recently, there have been few studies and scientific research about a link between the modes of transmission of the pandemic and the physical characteristics of the air inhaled through the respiratory tract. Doctors are now finding, without explaining it, that the most active spread is that of asymptomatic patients who do not have visible symptoms of breathing. It is for this reason that we focus our research on pulmonary aerosols of invisible spectrum. The medical studies carried out to date have been devoted to main clinical knowledge such as the definition and biological representation of the genome, the medical description of the viral cycle, that of receptor binding, fusion, transcription and replication of the virus propagation cycle. These studies have clarified the biochemical structure of the virus as well as the modes of action of the proteins in the Virus, such as the role of ACE2 receptors. Epidemiological studies found in the scientific literature have addressed the epidemic potential of MERS-CoV and the identification of the basic reproductive rate of patients infected with MERS-CoV without addressing the role of climatic variations.

Among these studies, the first was that of the first human coronaviruses studied, 229E (HCoV-229E) and OC43 (HCoV-OC43). These coronavirus were

isolated by researchers in the 1960s and are classified respectively among the Alpha coronaviruses and beta coronaviruses. In 2002, the first highly pathogenic coronavirus emerged in the human population, the beta coronavirus SARS-Co (2). It was responsible for an epidemic of severe acute respiratory syndromes that began in China. The following coronaviruses 229E (HCoV-229E) and OC43 (HCoV-OC43) were isolated in the 1960s. Following these epidemics of SARS-CoV, new coronaviruses, human beta coronaviruses NL63 (HCoV-NL63) and HKU1 were respectively discovered in 2004 and in 2005 and are responsible for mild infections. Then there was the appearance of beta coronavirus in Saudi Arabia. It was named Middle East Respiratory Coronavirus Syndrome (MERS-CoV). It appears from all the studies carried out in medical circles that coronaviruses are mainly transmitted by aerosols of biological fluids and by contamination of surfaces. They are said to infect the human airways by entering the cells of the respiratory epithelium through the apical pole. Recently, medical studies have been able to prove that the new virions being also excreted from the apical pole, facilitating the spread of the virus by coughing and sneezing (15).

Despite all the high-level medical studies carried out, despite modern medical imaging tools, results of treatment prescriptions are stagnating, attempts to eliminate the proliferation of the new coronavirus have so far been unsuccessful. Recent theoretical knowledge of the COVID-19 chemical attack is today at the highest medical level, but paradoxically it is lagging behind in obtaining effective medical treatments. Because of these noted difficulties, it becomes important to redirect scientific research and hope to obtain more encouraging results by focusing our efforts on research on invisible pulmonary aerosols. As the basis of our new study, we use the recently made observation that the virus is transmitted by aerosol of asymptomatic patients who mix with each other without contact. It is said that inhaled air is a major factor in the transmission of the virus. For this reason, we have devoted ourselves to examining the impact of changes in atmospheric characteristics on propagation velocities and to understanding the mechanism. The first parameter chosen is the daily variation of atmospheric relative humidity, because it is linked to the water vapor inhaled during respiration. The second parameter chosen is the variation in daily air

temperature because the effectiveness of viruses is known to be sensitive to temperatures. It is known that coronavirus succumb under very high temperatures, proliferate at moderate temperatures between 10 and 40 degrees and doze for negative temperatures.

We first identified daily fluctuations in atmospheric data on the same place in France and compared them with the data for the spread of the pandemic. The conclusions obtained were the subject of a verification of results on a series of 27 European countries, having very different climates, that is, some with hot and humid Mediterranean climate, others with cold and continental climate dry and the last in a cold and humid northern climate. We compared the climatic effects by presenting our results in the form of a graph with comparative evolution curves and in the form of correlations in XY axes.

Consequently, the novelty of our approach is to orient scientific interest to the examination of the characteristics of inhaled air during a pandemic period, to determine and understand the role of the atmosphere as a vector carrying COVID-19 in the pandemic.

EXPERIMENTATION

The examination of the mode of transport and spread of the virus is based on a survey of official atmospheric records for the periods of February, March and April 2020. The atmospheric data used are extracted from the Institut France Météorologie, in the northeast region of the hexagon due to the significant presence of viruses. The coronavirus data come from the French governmental bases of pandemic of COVID 19. We have with these data carried out correlation analyzes between the different data collected and performed the calculations and graphs with Excel software. The measurement point curves were smoothed by degree 6 polynomial regression of type $aX^6 + bX^5 + cX^4 + dX^3 + eX^2 + fX + g$. For the study of the daily monitoring, the two parameters, the daily humidity in France as well as the increase in cases of COVID19 were noted daily at the two humidity variation cycles, at 7 am and 4 pm: This schedule was chosen because the results at 7 am reflect the relaxation of absolute humidity during the cooling of the night, ie the increase in relative humidity until saturation in the morning. The results at 4 p.m. correspond to the hour when the daytime temperature is maximum, and correspond to the time of the day with the maximum humidity accumulation between 9 a.m. and 4 p.m. The monitoring of daily fluctuations is shown in Figure 1. The results of the linear correlation analysis of the readings at 7 a.m. and 4 p.m. are shown in Figures 2 and 3 respectively.

RESULTS

Figure 1 presents a comparison graph with superimposed curves of the simultaneous variations of three parameters, humidity at 7 o'clock, humidity at 16 o'clock and cases declared over a period from February 3 to April 30, days numbered from 1 to 40. Two periods characteristic trends stand out: At the start of the pandemic, a first period characterized by a rapid increase in the number of confirmed cases (day 1 to 8). A second period of 36 days is characterized by a short level of values followed by a continuous decrease until the last day. Period 2 between days 6 and 15 shows a daily fluctuation relationship (Figure 1) between the number of cases and the humidity.

Figure 1

The existing relationship between these two parameters is shown again in XY representation (Figures 2 and 3). The results in the figure show a relationship between the daily humidity values and the cases of coronavirus with a correlation coefficient of 45% for the 7 hour readings

Figure 2

For the 16 hour readings (figure 3). the figure show a relationship between the daily humidity

values and the cases of coronavirus with a correlation coefficient of 69%.

◆ Cases uncrease x 100
— Linéaire (Cases uncrease x 100)

Figure 3

Country	Cases 01 May per million	Average Humidity March April (%)
Germany	1966,1	56
Austria	1753,4	55
Belgium	4285,8	67
Bulgaria	227,8	52
Chipre	715,7	
Croatia	513,7	49
Denmark	1639,9	56
Spain	4560,2	73
Estonia	1285,9	64
Finland	924,8	63
France	2497,9	65
Greece	242,3	44
Hungary	296,6	51
Ireland	4273,7	62
Italy	3432,5	63
Latvia	451,5	59
Lithuania	499,6	58
Luxembourg	6250,0	70
Malte	964,9	62
Netherlands	2321,4	64
Poland	345,0	54
Portugal	2469,9	67
Czech Republic	724,4	51
Romania	647,3	43
United Kingdom	2688,8	66
Slovakia	256,9	51
Slovenia	675,1	51
Sweden	2113,0	66

Table 1

The humidity readings represent a regional sample of 80% of people in France (northeast region). The COVID 19 case reports in France correspond to the entire national population. The correlation coefficient obtained is equal to 65%. This is a sufficient confidence result to establish that there is a cause and effect relationship between relative humidity measured at 4 p.m. and cases of coronavirus.

Figure 4 is an epidemic representation of 27 European countries in XY axes. This figure compares the relative humidities and the numbers of coronaviruses. (See Table 1 values).

RELATIVE HUMIDITY TOWARDS CORONAVIRUS CASES FOR 27 EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

Figure 4

The elongated shape of the points reflects the existence of an increasing relationship between humidity and cases of coronavirus with a correlation coefficient of 77%. On the linear correlation curve, we find singularities related to temperature: several countries with the same X, Y coordinates, that is to say, with the same humidity and quantities of coronavirus, have very different temperatures. As an example, Spain and Ireland, which are known to be two countries with different climates, one Mediterranean, the other Nordic, have the particularity of having similar values of humidity and number of coronaviruses while the temperatures are very different (11 and 18 degrees)

Figure 5

However, in the opposite direction (FIG. 5) showing the temperature and the number of coronaviruses in XY axes, the figure shows a random point cloud with a very low correlation coefficient of 45%. The example of these two countries among others, reported in Figure 4 demonstrates that temperature is not a basic cause and effect parameter with the pandemic.

DISCUSSION

Medical institutes at this time know that active spread of the virus is present in asymptomatic patients who do not have visible breathing problems, such as coughing or sputum. Researchers at GUANGZHOU University in China have obtained medical images that the lungs of asymptomatic patients have pulmonary MRI coronavirus profiles. It follows from their work that invisible spectrum aerosols are contagious. The characteristic of aerosols is that their existence is dependent on a process of enlargement of droplets according to the dimension scale below. In this scale, the spectrum of water vapor is located between 1 Angstrom to 1 mm.

Figure 6

Principe de development of an aerosol

Figure 7 Ref 16*

The existence of a stable aerosol is linked to specific thermodynamic conditions. In order for water vapor molecules to agglomerate, accumulate and condense, they must comply with Kelvin's thermodynamic law figure 8.

For the aerosol of a patient, (17 *) the mucous membranes of the upper airways being abundantly vascularized, they ensure the humidification and warming of the inspired air. Under normal

conditions, the inspired air is brought to around 32 ° C and has been completely humidified when it leaves the pharynx. It is in the middle trachea that, normally, the air is brought to body temperature (37 ° C) and that it reaches the required degree of hygrometry, namely: 44 mg / l.

Figure 8

Therefore, in the opposite direction of the flow, when the air is discharged from the middle trachea to the pharynx, due to the passage from 37 ° to 32 ° the air is in supersaturation of vapor. Clapeyron's thermodynamic law of vapor pressure gives for a saturation at 37 degrees, a supersaturation pressure or relative humidity of 1.30 (Figure 9)

Figure 9

According to an expiration scenario using this data, the aerosol of supersaturated vapor cools

from 37 to 32 degrees when it leaves the pharynx, condenses under the conditions of Kelvin's thermodynamic law. The calculations of this law, for a saturation vapor overpressure coefficient located between 100 and 130, give a diameter of drops in thermodynamic equilibrium, between 4 and 100 nanometers. According to this law, the drops of dimension greater than the equilibrium curve fulfill the conditions of agglomeration and accumulation with each other. The law therefore demonstrates the existence of an aerosol invisible to the eye (less than 100 nanometers) when the expelled aerosol is close to the reference of supersaturation 130% relative humidity, i.e., an inhaled atmosphere of 100% d humidity, usual case in winter. The measurements obtained were an average relative humidity measured was 80% in March and 65% in early April, 55% in late April. These humidities correspond to 110% and 95% and 85% of relative humidity rejected. According to Kelvin's law, the aerosols rejected have droplet diameters of 11 nanometers in March, and 100 nanometers in early April and > 100 nanometers in late April. Beyond 100 nanometers, the droplets become too large to coagulate according to Kelvin's law, which corresponds to the observation at the end of April of the tendency to decrease in the number of coronaviruses declared.

Knowing that the spikes of coronavirus ends are hydrophilic, when the coagulation conditions of the vapor molecules allow it, the aerosol coagulates on the crown of spikes (Figure 10)

coagulation of molecules on hydrophilic spikes

Figure 10

Indeed, the coronavirus polypeptides have two endings (figure 11), one S1 with amino terminus NH₂, the other S2 with carbonyl end COO⁻ and the NH₂ end is hydrophilic (ref 18 *).

Spike configuration with N termination of hydrophilic S1 branch (ref 8)

Figure 11

The development of the coronavirus is due to the mechanism of infection which causes the additional release of water, the virions being carried away by the water vapor. These high humidity conditions exist in the lungs of an infected patient:

Mucous fluids in the lungs have been found to be overabundant during COVID 19 symptoms. Recent findings by hospital services obtained from patients with COVID 19 show images of MRI examination with a tapestry significant viral mucus in the alveoli. Biological analyzes show that the alveolar mucus is made up of 99% H₂O (13*). However, the mechanism of attack of cells by the coronavirus consists in creating protein ruptures by hydrolysis, that is to say with the production precisely of H₂O.

In detail of the attack mechanism, the COVID 19 viruses are characterized by their crown of proteins known as "Spike" or S. The SARS-Cov2 virus (COVID 19) begins by undergoing a "priming" stage for spikes, a kind of 'activation. COVID 19 Spikes are activated by their own enzyme. As a result, at the start of the viral attack, COVID 19, with its own enzymes, produces H₂O. Once the Spike protein is "awarded" or activated, the coronavirus will once again release water by hydrolysis. It will attach to one of the receptors on the surface of our cells, called ACE2. (Figure 12). Since the SARS-Cov2 has an envelope (Figure 12), it must indeed combine it with the membrane of our cells or of our cellular compartments to penetrate it.

This step, called endocytosis, requires that the Spike protein be cut again by a protease and therefore produce water a second time. Again, this is furin and TMPRSS2. Furin is a serine protease which catalyzes the cleavage of a polypeptide typically at the level of a basic sequence of the form -Arg - Xaa- (Arg / Lys) -Arg- | - where Xaa represents an acid residue any proteinogenic α-amino. TMPRSS2 codes for a protein in the serine protease family. Serine proteases are a family of different proteases called peptidases, which share the same mechanism of action. Like all proteases, their function is to cleave proteins or peptides by hydrolyzing their peptide bonds.

Figure 12

The coronavirus also releases water a third time, by repairing errors in its RNAs. It does this because it has its own enzymes in the genome whose role is, on the one hand, to repair the errors of its RNAs and, on the other hand, to ensure the replication of virions. Its own proteases therefore create additional hydrolysis, thus an addition of H₂O

Therefore, the mechanism of the coronavirus produces a cascade of water molecules. The finding of overabundant liquid in medical imaging is evidence of the excess of hydrolysis reactions, the so-called hydrolysis. When this excess alveolar mucus, in the terminal stage of the disease, invades all the pulmonary alveoli, it constitutes a thick barrier which reduces the exchange of oxygen. In addition, the excess alveolar mucus, because it consists essentially of 99% (13) of H₂O actively participates in an overabundant evaporation of water vapor at the time of expiration. COVID 19 is not destroyed by H₂O but on the contrary, it adapts perfectly to the abundance of liquid mucus: For this, Figure 12 shows that it is made up of three main layers, the RNA genome in the center, an envelope of proteins and esterase and an outer crown of Spike glycoproteins. The COVID 19 Spike glycoprotein is located in the outer ring and at the same time is hydrophilic. Looking on its affinity for water and the abundant presence of particles of water vapor exhaled by the lungs, the virion, being surrounded by coagulated H₂O on its crown, is entrained in the exhaled humid air. Then, water vapor from the pulmonary alveoli brings the COVID 19 virion

Other climatic worsening

The increase in water vapor can also be increased by the high humidity of the air in winter. The more the amount of water vapor expired, the more the amount of virion entrained. Not only the amount of vapor exhaled by a healthy patient is increased by the hydrolysis effect of the coronavirus, but even, it can be increased by the inspired atmospheric humidity. During a period saturated with humidity (95%) such as the period of days 1 to 15 of our survey, the excess of inspired atmospheric water vapor is more important than usual. In this case, the production of H₂O by hydrolysis of the coronavirus is superabundant on breathing out.

Otherwise, for less humid periods, such as days 15 to 45 of our survey shown in the graph of Figure 1, the atmospheric supply of breathe in vapor is less, and therefore the quantity of exhaled water vapor is more limited. We found these trends in the results of Figure 1. We observe on our curves such variations, that is to say increases during humid atmosphere of declared COVID 19 cases, and conversely, decreases in cases in a drier atmosphere. These correlation findings clearly show that there is a cause and effect relationship between the humidity of the inspired atmospheric air and the daily number of reported cases.

Looking on our results, water vapor plays a major role in the proliferation of the COVID 19. Other Studies support our conclusions: It is indeed known through the multiple studies of all the viruses that have developed for twenty years, that excess hydrolysis has come from the action of proteases. We have proof of the role of protease hydrolysis because the blocking of proteases has been successful in stopping the pandemic of the ZIKA virus which belongs to the same family of viruses. Like the COVID 19, the ZIKA virus is an envelope virus encapsulating an RNA genome, as does the COVID 19 Coronavirus. More precisely, regarding hydrolysis, the ZIKA virus has been proven to be hydrolyzed into three structural proteins. (E, prM / M and C) and seven non-structural proteins (NS1, NS2A, NS2B, NS3, NS4A, NS4B and NS5) by the host and viral proteases.

ZIKA has been successfully treated with drugs that block proteases. So, the hydrolysis of viral proteases from COVID 19, because the virus belongs to the same family of enveloped viruses, can also be blocked by blocking drugs as has been done for the ZIKA virus in which the activity of proteases and in particular NS2B -NS3 has been blocked.

Our results can help to carry out a prospective study on the date of the end of proliferation of COVID 19. We have shown that the relative humidities allow only the propagation of the virus by transport with water vapor when they are higher than 80%. Sufficient humidity in March, became insufficient at the end of April, and the values coincide with the slowdown of the pandemic. As a result, our encouraging correlation calculations make it possible to estimate of the likely date on which the pandemic's proliferation will stop. Extrapolating the measurements represented by the correlation in Figure 3, shows that the minimum humidity obtained between 15 and 20% corresponds on our graphs to the number of cases declared from 500 to 600 per day. If we base on the reference of the climatic conditions of the year 2019 (figure 13), the waited humidity rates of 15-20% are at the beginning of May, which corresponds on the curve to the end of the pandemic. Note that the correlation curve (Figure 13) does not pass through the origin. This property of the curve could indicate that an activity has not

become zero, and that the coronavirus is slippery. In such a case, the return of humidity to the winter seasons could allow it to reappear.

with cases of coronavirus declared low, in the order of 500 per day, and that these values correspond to reality. This finding has a major novelty effect, among widely established diagnoses, that the spread is caused by the expulsion of cough from large droplets.

End Matter

Author Contributions and Notes

The author did not benefit from any contributory intervention for the writing of the manuscript and declares the authors no conflict of interest. This article contains publicly available online support information and images. He declares to be in compliance with the availability of all the data mentioned in the manuscript, as well as links to all the data hosted in an external repository.

He states that all relevant ethical guidelines have been followed, all necessary IRB and / or ethics committee approvals are not required, no patients have been diagnosed or consulted. No clinical trials have been performed and needed to be registered.

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■ Humidity
■ Temperature 16 h

Figure 13

CONCLUSION

Our results on reported COVID 19 cases and humidity revealed cause and effect relationships during two months of the pandemic. The effect of the meteorological environment observed in the northeast area of France, where the major pandemic focus is located (the city of Metz was chosen as the benchmark test), reveals a cause and effect relationship between the rate humidity and the daily occurrence of new cases of Coronavirus reported. For the period March to April 2020, there is a perceptible correlation in the studied period of the pandemic. We have shown that the viral mechanism is favored by the aerosol with droplets from 4 to 100 nanometers, invisible to the eye. We have concluded from our work that proliferation can occur by breathing out of vapor, causing water virions in patients without symptoms of cough. This conclusion has a major novelty effect among the widely established diagnoses. The mechanism that we describe is that the water vapor contained in the alveolar mucus is the aerosol transport vector of COVID 19. For water vapor to be the means of transport of COVID 19, we explained that the Spikes of COVID 19, because they are hydrophilic, create special bonds with H₂O, Van der Waals type bonds. COVID 19 is surrounded by coagulation of water molecules and entrained by exhaled water vapor. We found that the low humidities (20%) on the graphs coincide

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